

GMPi: Global Myocardial Performance Index.

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Provisional Results of Original Research (GMPi-Study)

The new echocardiographic index has been evaluated against EF for diagnosing heart failure in two subgroups based on LV filling pressure: $E/e' < 8$ and $E/e' \leq 8$.

ROC analysis demonstrated the **superiority of GMPi over EF** in diagnosing heart failure, regardless of E/e' values. The **Area Under the ROC Curve (AUC)** confirmed **GMPi's excellent to good discriminatory ability**, whereas EF exhibited **poor discriminatory performance** in both groups.

Furthermore, the **Overall Model Quality supports GMPi's significantly greater explanatory power** in heart failure diagnosis compared to EF, highlighting its potential as a more reliable diagnostic tool.

Area Under the ROC Curve

Test Result Variable(s)	E/Ea	Area
GMP-index	< 8.0000	.837
	>= 8.0000	.762
EF	< 8.0000	.271
	>= 8.0000	.322

Metric	EF (E/e' < 8)	GMPi (E/e' < 8)	EF (E/e' ≤ 8)	GMP (E/e' ≤ 8)
AUC (ROC Curve)	0.271 (Poor)	0.838 (Excellent)	0.322 (Poor)	0.762 (Good)
Overall Model Quality	0.20 (Very Low)	0.79 (High)	0.26 (Low)	0.71 (High)

